

3rd INAS-enKORE Workshop

Taming complexity in ecology: Novel approaches for theory development, enhanced argumentation and knowledge synthesis

Villa Frieden, Hotel & Seminarhaus, Esplanade 6, Bad Blankenburg

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Abstract

Machine learning is getting more and more available for researchers outside the domain of computer sciences. For example, statistical methods for data mining that build on machine learning (e.g. random forests) are increasingly applied in ecology. These methods help with analyzing the increasing amounts of available data, thus allowing to identify existing patterns and develop predictions. When it comes to uncovering theoretical insights and understanding mechanisms, however, different approaches are needed. Given the immense complexity ecology has to deal with, it seems obvious that there have to be ways how computer and information science could be leveraged for aiding the field with theory development as well.

In this third enKORE-INAS workshop, an interdisciplinary group of 32 experts from ecology, computer, data and information science, computational linguistics, philosophy of science and other fields came together to discuss possibilities for advancing theory development in ecology. The 2.5 days in-person workshop featured short presentations and much time for organized discussions as well as interdisciplinary exchange. This workshop summary documents some of our discussions.

Participants

Name		Affiliation
Al Mustafa	Tarek	University of Jena
Alamanciak	Tim	University of Waterloo, Canada
Algergawy	Alsayed	University of Jena
Bengel	Lars	FernUniversität in Hagen
Bernard-Verdier	Maud	IGB & FU Berlin
Bocci	Federica	University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Brinner	Marc	University of Bielefeld
Dawson	Wayne	University of Liverpool, UK
De Meester	Luc	IGB Berlin
D'Souza	Jennifer	TIB Hanover
Heger	Tina	IGB & FU Berlin
Jeschke	Jonathan	IGB & FU Berlin
Karam	Naouel	InfAI
König-Ries	Birgitta	University of Jena
Laubach	Zachary	University of Colorado, Boulder
Lokatis	Sophie	FU Berlin
Macedo	Rafael	IGB & FU Berlin
Maia	Midierison	Humber Institute of Technology & Advanced Learning, CA
Meyerson	Laura	University of Rhode Island, USA
Mietchen	Daniel	IGB & FU Berlin
Millard	Joe	Natural History Museum, London, UK
Musseau	Camille	IGB & FU Berlin
Parreño	Alejandra	TU Munich
Santana	Carlos	UPenn
Spake	Rebecca	University of Reading, UK
Travassos-Britto	Bruno	University of Toronto, Canada
Vogt	Lars	TIB Hanover
Wagner	Tobias	Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt
Wahl	Jonas	TU Berlin & DLR Jena
Wollrab	Sabine	IGB Berlin
Wood	Justin	UCLA
Zarriß	Sina	Univesity of Bielefeld

Part I: Introduction

Introductory presentation

Welcome and introduction to the INAS and enKORE projects and the general Hi Knowledge initiative - INAS and enKORE teams

Aims of the workshop

- [Hi Knowledge](#) Initiative – Towards an Atlas of Knowledge
 - Given what we have and what we did:
 - What are reasonable next steps?
 - How can we better connect to the work of others?
- Taming complexity in ecology:
 - When building this Atlas of Knowledge:
 - How can we best account for complexity and context dependence?
 - When synthesizing evidence from diverse case studies:
 - How can we get from describing patterns to understanding causes?
- During the workshop especially:
 - In-depth exchange on questions and potential solutions
 - Formation of new collaborations

Introduction of participants

Every participant was asked to write their name and field of expertise on a moderation card. The cards were pinned on a board, and we arranged the cards so that the diversity of fields of research, and the clusters of people working on similar things became visible.

Part II: Knowledge synthesis and knowledge graphs

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 11:30 – 11:50 | What is evidence in biodiversity science? A philosophical perspective
<i>Federica Bocchi</i> |
| 11:50 – 12:10 | Challenges with using meta-analysis to addressing context-dependence in ecology
<i>Rebecca Spake</i> |
| 12:10 – 12:30 | Cross-threat meta-analytic synthesis for robust predictions of insect biodiversity change
<i>Joe Millard</i> |
| 13:30 – 13:50 | The PATH approach for knowledge synthesis in ecology
<i>Bruno Travassos-Britto</i> |
| 13:50 – 14:10 | SCINEXT: Neural-Symbolic Innovation EXtraction
<i>Jennifer D'Souza</i> |
| 14:10 – 14:30 | BiodivPortal: an ontology repository and service for biodiversity
<i>Naouel Karam</i> |
| 14:30 – 14:50 | Semantic annotation of ecology research with the Open Research Knowledge Graph
<i>Maud Bernard-Verdier & Lars Vogt</i> |
| 14:50 – 15:10 | Introducing Researchmaps.org
<i>Justin Wood</i> |

Tools fair

Data scientists, AI experts, modelers etc demoed their work, and workshop participants were invited to walk around and visit the 'stands'.

The following tools were on display:

- [ORKG](#) for ecologists (Maud Bernard-Verdier and Lars Vogt)
- [ORKG for virologists](#) (Jennifer D'Souza)
- BioDiv Portal (Naouel Karam)
- Wikidata / Scholia (Daniel Mietchen)
- LLMs for analysing hypotheses in texts (Marc Brinner)
- Computational linguistic models in academic texts (Carlos Santana)
- Internucleos AI (Midierson Maia)
- [Researchmaps.org](#) (Justin Wood)
- Causal inference Software package (Jonas Wahl)

Reflection and discussion

Topics that were mentioned during the discussion after the tools fair:

- We need to find good ways of integrating AI in our workflows
- We need better ontologies and better integration of ontologies into other tools
- Causality is quite an important topic
- Co-design is key (designing without domain experts can lead to frustrating results)
- We need to work on the nexus connecting challenges in computer science and ecology. What are the topics that experts from both fields are excited about?
- Think about using restoration type as a starting point for building causal models as alternative to starting with hypotheses (as in Hi Knowledge projects) or experiments (as in Researchmaps.org)
- Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) seem highly interesting for ecology. We should think about ways to publish them (=> dedicated nanopublications?)
- We need a workflow that makes sure we don't make mistakes when transferring tools and approaches outside of the realm they have been developed for
- Ontologies so far are meant for machines and developers, but they could be so useful for ecologists and other domain experts as well
- LLMs and reliability: How can LLMs be improved and applied without making mistakes?
- Benefits of standardization versus its downsides – there seem to be a trade-offs:
 - We want to have tools with broad applicability
 - But we don't want to lose the connection to the context
 - We want to be able to 'act local' with the knowledge matching the local situation and not some average ('think global, act local')
- Similar trade-off: describing the use of language versus trying to standardize language use
- How can we turn tools developed during a project into permanent infrastructure?
- Commercial versus open science
- How can we capture the nuances in ecology with the researchmaps.org tool?
- In general, there is a lot of overlap in interests, but also domain-specific idiosyncrasies

Wednesday, 28 February 2024

Part III: Causal inference in ecology

- 09:10 – 09:30 Applying causal inference in ecology and evolution
Zachary Laubach
- 09:30 – 09:50 Causal network graphs in ecology
Alejandra Parreño
- 09:50 – 10:10 Argumentation-based causal reasoning
Lars Bengel
- 10:10 – 10:30 Discovering causal relations from data
Jonas Wahl

Group work and discussion

Already during Day 1, we had asked all participants to provide their questions concerning the overall topic of the workshop by writing them on moderation cards. We organized these questions in clusters which then became the overarching topics for breakout group discussions.

Clusters of questions and topics collected by workshop participants

Tools for stakeholders

- Knowledge co-production: How to bridge disciplinary boundaries and foster stakeholder engagement?
- How can we use these tools to bridge the divide between researchers and practitioners / policy makers?
 - How can we design these meta-scientific tools to serve policy / practice?
 - How can we best use novel computational tools to bridge gaps between disciplines and stakeholders?
- Open science vs. capitalism?

Causality

- Mechanistic models / experiments, evidence versus correlations
- How to connect data to causal networks
- What are the main ways in which ecologists answer questions of cause and effect? What data are typically used?

Context dependence

- What if everything is terribly context-dependent? How to deal with this?
- How to account for context dependence in synthesis?

- How to account for context dependencies when quantifying supported / rejected hypotheses?
- What are the biotic interactions that every introduced and naturalized plant species is involved in, and how do these interactions affect invasion success and impact? [is there something that is not context dependent about invasions?]
- Biases and unrepresentative datasets
- How to formalize uncertainties?

Human – machine tensions

- Automated text extraction methods?
- Individual versus standardized publications / terminologies / ontologies / tools
- How can we become more effective in creating machine-actionable and human-actionable data and knowledge?
- How to use ontology knowledge with NLP tools?
- Motivating and enabling ecologists to curate AI and other tools' outputs
- How can AI or other machines help efforts of manual curation like Wikidata etc? Or is manual annotation soon obsolete?

Interdisciplinarity: ecology and computer science

- How can semantic services support ecology / ecologists?
- Interdisciplinary research: what do you need from computer science?
- How can we operationalize these tools in publishing in major publication houses?
- What are the similarities and differences between prompt optimization and systematic literature search?
- How the new tools of access to information will shape practices, and knowledge structure in the future?
- How to formalize hypotheses and how to link data to this formalization?
- How can tools handle idiosyncrasies in specific disciplines?
- How can we share curation workflows?
- What are comfortable salient research facets of invasion biology research?
- As an ecologist, when you are writing a publication, how do you think which hypotheses (argument) to be included in abstract?

Break-out group discussions

1 Tools for stakeholders

Which stakeholders to address?

Policymakers, Practitioners, Science Communicators/Educators, Environmental NGOs, Industry

What information does each stakeholder group need?

- Form of input acceptable to stakeholder group
- Consider features outside traditional ecology that matter to stakeholder group
- Create personas -> Josh and Vanessa

Josh the Practitioner/Policy maker

- He focuses on that particular geographical range
- Has an expansive job description
- Has little ability to do targeted research
- Has no access to commercial databases (Web of Science or Scopus)
- Is accountable to (i) interest groups and (ii) administrative officials
- Works on regular hours (9 to 5 job)?
- Notable to do effective long-term monitoring and adaptive planning
- Has to make decisions quickly
- Isolated: is not sitting close to other domain experts
- Is not conversant in technical research terms
- Poor institutional memory

Desiderata for Josh's Data Synthesis Tool

- Free & open (with reasonable exceptions, e.g. to not reveal the exact location of individuals of highly threatened species)
- Social tools, so that Josh can connect to other practitioners/policymakers and researchers working on similar topics
- Modular & customizable
- Place/geography ontology & geotagging
- Intuitive to use
- Representation of evidence & consensus
- Ability for 'Joshes' (practitioners/policymakers) to contribute to the tool's content as well
- Tool should be connected with similar and cross-disciplinary tools (e.g. Conservation Evidence)
- Should facilitate context-typing: (i) focal environmental problem, (ii) focal geographic range, (iii) focal ecosystem type
- Broader than ecology

Vanessa the Journalist

- Calls NGOs

- Needs “expert” testimony
- Likes soundbites
- Is on a tight deadline
- Trustworthiness and transparency are important
- Uses academics for background/context
- Asks PR offices for whom to talk to
- Output is short & fast
- Wants a short list of key takeaways
- Local interest
- Is looking for ways to find and contact experts, and to map expertise

Desiderata for Vanessa’s Data Synthesis Tool

- The tool is not a substitute for personal expertise -> e.g. an AI tool might give misleading numbers -> warning in the tool
- Tool should communicate complexity & nuance in simple ways
- Search function to find domain experts (editable by domain experts); pictures, sound bites and/or videos related to these experts and information on how to pronounce their name, perhaps even suggest topics/questions that these experts could be asked (but this point was controversial in the breakout group)
- Tool should illustrate “camps” within the field, so that Vanessa can contact experts from different camps if she wants
- Tool should highlight any potential Conflicts of Interest or other red flags related to Vanessa’s topic of interest
- Tool should represent some sort of agreement/disagreement/consensus in the literature/field
- Searchability: similarity, temporal, geographical (geotagging)
- Highlighting trends & noteworthiness, perhaps also controversial topics
- Tool should provide access to open/free images/figures, videos, recordings with an indication of their reliability (if they are authentic)
- Focus on ecology, but also covering other fields: possibility to map/filter for discipline
- Prioritize accuracy over shininess
- Should link to previous relevant journalism/news pieces

2 Causality and context dependence

Top part of the flip chart:

- There is a trade-off between causality and context-dependence
- We can regard the different methods applied in ecology as situated on a gradient covering different parts of this trade-off
- Relationship between degree of control (high in lab experiments, very low in observational studies) and the ratio between causality and context dependence: The more control the more causal knowledge can be gained

1. Experimental approach for direct test of causality

- lab experiments: lot of control
- field experiments: less control

2. If on observational data, other methods:

- Statistical matching - Paul Ferraro in conservation science
- Causal models/Pearl approach - see also Jim Grace (structural equation modeling)
- using time series as some way to disentangle loops

Using causal graphs: synthesis methods distinguishing observational from interventional (experimental) datasets, adding information about the context in which data was collected.

- AIs could help inform/design these graphs instead of/in complement of domain experts?
- AI: integrate better findability, used as co-pilots
- AI being able to judge quality of papers and exclude some studies, even if their claims are in our scope on the surface

Difference between causal models and prediction:

- predictive models are not able to deal with changes in mechanisms or context, whereas causal relations/mechanistic models might?
- Causality is more about explanation than prediction.
- But in ecology, causal relationships can also break in a different context.

Lower part of the flip chart:

- Context dependence can mean that we observe a causal relationship in one situation ($z=1$) but not in another ($z=0$)
- We could model this also as z being a moderator of x and y
- Or rather as a moderator of the relationship between x and y
- Or on function connecting x and y
- What should the model look like? Can there be arrows on arrows?

Add data to causal networks (e.g. hypotheses networks) and include context dependence: e.g. context might change which causal links are valid or become invalid.

- data feeding the network should be tagged with
 - data quality
 - whether it was tested and eliminated
 - context (taxa, habitat, etc.)
- identify where more experiments are needed
- identify which links are not really relevant
- links could have information on whether these are necessary and sufficient causes
- identifying data/research gaps

General remarks

- Whether something is cause or context depends on the question asked
- Accounting for context may mean to extract different narratives from the same graph

Challenges to account for:

- Quality of studies: how to decide which studies to include?
- Abstracts don't carry all relevant information
- Dependency not only on context, also on analyst
- Big journals often demand general statements! This counteracts reporting on context

Ideas for solutions

- "Constraints on Generality": COG statement = to what extent would these results hold (= population tested, existing bias, estimand and prediction)

- This is mandatory in psychology -> statements that need to be made in psychology journals. Refers to a standardized way we should be writing our results
- Suggestion: this should be mandatory for ecological papers as well
- But: do these statements really make sense? Or could we always only state: we don't know what happens in a different context?
- Keep in mind causal heterogeneity (see Elliot-Graves 2016, DOI 10.1007/s10539-015-9504-0)
 - Causal relationships often 'break' at some point (e.g. if abiotic conditions change)
 - It does not seem to be the case that causal relationships are necessarily more robust than correlations
- Make abstracts more informative and transfer every human-written abstract into a machine interpretable form
- Use a modular approach for building causal graphs
- Where to find the nodes? AI Assistant! Either: feed it all the papers and let it extract possible contexts; create vector representations and train a model. Or: skip the feature extraction and just feed texts?
- Use model comparisons to compare different variants of causal graphs

Open questions

- How to identify nodes in the causal graphs e.g. from papers?
 - What granularity to model?
- Broad statements and tests of parts of that (Enemy release works in setting a,b,c)
- Are there ecological principles that work across species and ecosystem?
 - Are there causal relationships that are more fundamental than others?
 - Are they more easy to discover e.g. in community ecology, but in invasion ecology they are 'concealed' e.g. by anthropogenic effects causing deviations, or terminological ambiguities?
 - Could it be possible to establish fundamental causal relationship with strongly controlled experiments, and then they are modulated by context, which we can discover with observational studies?
- Can we have families of causal diagrams?
- How to start building causal graphs
 - Should we start from full model and reduce it, or rather simple models that we build up?
 - How about starting with a big model containing all possible nodes and all possible arrows and then trim it down based on (experimental) results?
 - Jonas: for complex systems, use a modular approach: build smaller causal networks and connect them
 - question our construct validity: the concepts and hypotheses we are trying to capture are not necessarily what we measured.
 - go down to the basic mechanistic relationships or basic ecological processes as units of the model that are "always true" => not that easy, and people disagree.
 - Is it a problem to have different models when you ask different analysts ?
 - could test different models with data to see if it falsifies a graph
 - could provide a range of predictions/scenarios

- Could it be possible to train machines to predict the context from analyzing the paper / the abstract?
- Can a machine help ask a synthesis question about how much causation is addressed in our papers?
- What are the goals if we do manage to create these AI helped reliable causal models?
- How can AI help answer specific research questions? Or identify low hanging fruit research questions?

Related works that could be relevant:

<https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.1510507113> - Causal Inference and the Data Fusion Problem, discusses how to combine data from heterogeneous sources (e.g. observational and experimental) for Causal Inference

<https://hal.science/hal-03008276/document> - Causal inference methods for combining randomized trials and observational studies: a review

<https://academic.oup.com/jrsssb/article/78/5/947/7040653> - Invariant Causal Prediction

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.04952> - Some metrics for comparing causal graphs (pretty technical)

To be checked out as well: Hill's causal criteria

3 Humans and Machines

- How to motivate ecologists to use specific tools?
- Tools have to offer some clear benefits to the users, e.g. higher speed, lower effort, higher quality or higher interoperability
- How to build tools that help the ecologists do their research?
- Try to involve machines in the research workflow right from the beginning, e.g. express research questions or data management plans in a machine-actionable fashion.
- In software development, involve potential user communities from the start.
- Especially try to involve communities e.g. GLEON - Global Lake Ecological Observation Network: <https://gleon.org>
- Ecologists need to be aware that at least some of their data might be used outside their original project, e.g. for aggregation, benchmarking or quality control purposes.
- What to do if there is no usable ontology available for a specific use case?
- Can AI read the papers for ecologists, so as to facilitate meta analyses?
- Darwin Core is trying to address some of these problems: <https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>
- How can we do automated text extraction of specialist terms, for which there is not a lot of training data?
- <https://github.com/SuLab/mark2cure>

Discussion Round 2

- Are (LLM-like) AIs objective "machines" or rather regurgitating expert opinions?
- What are the differences among AIs / machines / automatic algorithms and statistical processes?

- differentiate also generative AI and other more focused AIs
- hard to know what we can trust with AIs that are new and we don't understand
- Can AIs help summarize large sets of papers into the main ideas?
- AIs as a member of the research group
- Some examples of how AIs can be used in teaching/research groups:
<https://www.wired.com/story/chatgpt-education-originality/>

Different branches of "machine" solutions to our problems:

- non-directed approaches based on natural language and no additional formalization efforts like NLP and LLM
- formalization and standardization via semantic modeling and top-down consensus approaches to make knowledge machine-readable.
- Can these be combined? (see the human-machine triangle below)

LLM AIs:

- as a baseline synthesis to spur original ideas (see again
<https://www.wired.com/story/chatgpt-education-originality/>)

Outstanding question: Can AIs be creative? Can they really generate novel ideas?

The Human-Machine triangle :) Two types of “machines” interact with humans: Machine learning AIs (typically LLMs, generative AIs like GPT-4, etc.) and Symbolic models (ontologies, knowledge graphs, causal graphs, etc.). The triangle attempts to map out the type of work humans and machines can and should do (in red) according to our discussion group. It is not all that they can do, but we tried to think about what we can imagine could be the most beneficial for knowledge and science. Example of things that can and should be done at the interface are also indicated (in grey) in the triangle, while feedback arrows indicate what each side brings to the other. (Complaints to be addressed to: Maud Bernard-Verdier, Bruno Travassos-Britto, Naouel Karem & Joe Millard.)

4 Interdisciplinary work (ecology & computer science)

- What do we need from computer science?
 - Computer scientists have the technical knowledge, but the two different sides have a disconnect—ecologists have the domain knowledge, and computer scientists technical
 - Problem of the literature review is aggregation and missing structure
- Putting the data into a common format, and then in computer science relying on the graph structure
- Graph structure gives a transparency to the ecological thought process and where the gaps are
- Difference in the way that computer scientists and ecologists think about causation/prediction.
 - Ecologists rings alarm bells when we talk about hypothesizing from the data (harking; potential p-hacking)
 - Has led to ecologists picking up idea of protocols and preregistration to try and increase reproducibility.
 - Computer scientists concerned with prediction, not so much 'causation' per se.
- Understand the environment, and make predictions
 - Tackling small hypotheses, isolating out for individual effects.
 - Continually updating the prior knowledge model according to our new knowledge about the world.
- Difficulty in choosing one model—perhaps we should be choosing multiple?
- What are similarities between prompt optimization and systematic review searching?
 - How can semantic service support ecology?
 - Studies using different vocabulary, same words different meaning
 - Concept has a meaning, so is different to words.
 - Problem of solving synonyms, ways of using knowledge graphs fits really well with taxonomic information and relatedness between species.
- Showed BioPortal and spoke about the mapping of traits—for making connections between studies
 - Context dependence between expert opinion and the empirical study.
 - Can traits be automatically extracted—helps reduce the workload for experts
- What are comparable facets of invasion biology research?
 - Hypotheses grouped into separate facets/themes, can be grouped hierarchy
 - 5 facets of invasion biology research: invasion success, invasion pathways, invasion management, meta-something, impact
 - Some groups didn't fit elsewhere (i.e. methods), so grouped into a meta category
- How to formalize hypotheses and how to link data to do this formalization?
 - Difficult to distill down a complex system into individual hypotheses.
- Figuring out what might be in between your cause and effect and isolate the cause
- How can we share curation workflows?
 - Sharing the steps to produce some results
 - Can GitHub fill this role? Perhaps not if it doesn't provide a record of the workflow.
 - Code and github could help, but still doesn't solve all of our problems.

- Interactive analysis to see whether more data will change the results.
- Make publishers try to make the data available, or publish as a data set
 - Should be a reject if don't make the data available because can't know that it's not reproducible.
 - Have to invite that person as an author—the collector has background domain knowledge, and perhaps just by talking to the collector you hadn't realised something important about the data.
 - Specific important notes that caveat the data—strange values can be explained if you get in touch with the data provider.
- A paper should be completely reproducible, from the raw data to the results.

5 From hypotheses to structured summaries

Hypothesis-based approach to filtering for ecology research

- In Computer Science, for instance, we have research-problem-based approach. Our search in search engines starts with a research problem. Translating this to ecological research, it appears that search begins with a hypothesis.
- Marc Brinner's tool classifying abstracts against hypotheses, based on the hypothesis taxonomy from Tina and Jonathan's work, works at present from the top-level of the taxonomy
- ongoing work to classify abstracts to sub-levels in the taxonomy
- uses LLMs to scope out portions of the abstract that indicate the hypothesis
- how to broaden the scope of testing similarity objectives by a pane listing similar papers
- expand the existing dataset of 950 annotated papers to a larger database of scholarly articles in Ecology research queried with the help of the hypotheses and then figure out if new hypotheses could be identified

<https://orkg.org/usecases/r0-estimates> Virology structured summaries and research question based filtered views of papers | this tool explores the prospect "from keywords to structured summaries: streamlining scholarly knowledge access" <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.14622>

- deriving from the ORKG model, structured comparisons are a distinct approach to reading research
- with more conversations with ecologists, could we enrich the hypothesis taxonomy with salient facets of ecological research at the lower levels of taxonomy, in particular, where it is specialized?
- then LLMs could be leveraged to determine a selection, classification, clustering, and structured summarizing workflow plugged into the large database of open-access papers in ecology (hoping that most papers have the full-text available).

Moderated general discussion

- Context-dependence is highly relevant for practice
 - Average conditions are not informative for management
 - External validity of a study is linked to this
 - The context of the practice is an additional layer that also has to be taken into account; it determines the questions that are being asked

- It is important to communicate the trade-off between knowledge on causation and on context dependence
- Ideally, context would be contained in the causal graph
 - There would be a ‘full model’ containing all the potential links between factors
 - This graph could be queried to find out about specific effects of the context
- The ‘full’ causal graph could be built in a modular way
- Participants discussed repeatedly whether there are causal connections that are more fundamental than others, e.g. those related to ‘basic processes’ like growth and reproduction or community assembly
 - If this was the case, these may be a good starting point for building causal graphs
 - Also, these might be more robust than others
- Question of robustness of causal connections
 - There is the idea that causal relationships could be more robust than correlational ones
 - It does not seem clear whether this really holds for ecological systems
- There is a challenge connected to granularity and hierarchical organization
 - Which level should the nodes in the causal graph address?
 - If it is a graph useful for ecology, it should probably not represent physiological processes, thus the nodes should not represent entities e.g. on a cellular level
 - Idea that came up: look for the level that seems most relevant for interventions
- What is urgently needed is a good notion of compatibility and transferability of different methods and approaches to representing context dependence and causality
- Good ways forward
 - Combining AI with structured information
 - Co-design, co-develop, work together across disciplines, from the start

Thursday, 29 February 2024

Summary of days 1 and 2

- Challenges for knowledge synthesis in ecology
 - What exactly is the ‘evidence’ we want to synthesize?
 - Some of our common approaches are not ideal
 - Major issues with statistical meta-analyses
 - Tendency to cherry-pick causes to report instead reporting in a more holistic way
 - Term ambiguities are hard to keep track of
 - Knowledge keeps getting lost
 - In translating from brains to text to formalized language
 - If we only analyze abstracts and not main texts
 - Datasets are not published in a way they can be easily found
 - Biases are strong and tend to get reproduced by AI
 - E.g. geographical and taxonomical biases

- Context is not only relevant for describing nature, but also for decision making and management
 - The tools therefore need to be able to give answers matching the context of the user (e.g. 'Josh')
- Good ideas
 - Consider context dependence and causality as trade-off for the design of empirical studies and data analysis
 - Working towards a more comprehensive model in a modular way
 - Allow for different versions of causal models (e.g. one per analyst) and use or develop model comparison and validation techniques
 - ...(there were many more)
- Other kinds of expertise relevant for future work
 - Sociology and Science and Technology Studies (STS), political theory: how do power relationships lead to biases etc. and how to change this?
 - STS, ethics: What are the societal and conceptual implications of using large language models and other AI driven tools in science?
- Potential ways forward
 - Formal logics and argumentation frameworks
 - Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) and causal inference frameworks
 - Combining AI and structured information
 - **Co-develop!** Collaborate across disciplines from the start

Part IV: AI for Interdisciplinary Research

09:15 – 09:35 Interdisciplinary Research with Internucleos: an AI designed by researchers, for researchers

Midierson Maia

Group work and discussion

We asked participants to formulate the research topic they would be interested in working on based on the results of the workshop, and clustered these topics into groups. These groups then became the topics for a last round of breakout-group discussions.

Clusters of questions and topics collected by workshop participants

Causal networks and modeling hypotheses

- Causal networks => local knowledge
- Evidence gaps, missing links
- Causal nets & ontologies, defining concepts, formalizing CNs
- Try out formal logics for invasion hypotheses
- How can we optimize / formalize ecologists' use of DAGs for modeling causality / hypotheses?
- How to combine arguments – causal networks; arguments – semantic web?
- Causal networks for invasion biology combined with argumentation machines

- Link to data
- Model causal links with nodes as measurable or actionable variables
- Apply causal graph modeling to invasion ecology
- Individualized versus standardized ontologies / causal networks

AI and ontology development / Using ontologies in AI

- Identify a good use case to develop workflows for knowledge production, identify barriers for researchers in existing workflows and develop AI and knowledge graph based solutions
- Work on solutions to interoperability issues (semantic or cognitive) and practical barriers to create knowledge graphs
- Integrate machine learning / large language models with structured data, especially with Wikidata
- Use LLMs and prompting to support technical workflows for ecologists
- Stabilize mechanisms to overlay terminologies of different granularities
- Restoration ecology:
 - Create ORKG template
 - Create restoration ecology ontology
 - Create restoration ecology wikidata page
- Applying language models developed for individual hypotheses (or evidence) from academic papers
 - Use grey literature (policy reports and guidelines, restoration programs...)
 - Identify relevance / prevalence of research hypotheses (or evidence)

- Build a database of publications in ecology. Get a sense of the landscape (% full-texts) available – this is needed for AI development
- Computer scientists need an overview of the data landscape in ecology / invasion biology
- Continue ORKG structured descriptions
- Think about relations of knowledge and data, especially how data comes to be and how that enables and limits knowledge practices in ecology

- Concept for integrating ontology knowledge in Marc's tool
- AI to enrich ontologies / taxonomies
- How to make use of available resources (data, publications, other) to validate hypotheses
- Finalize (?) Hypothesis Ontology and instantiate it for invasion biology (with a little help from AI)
- Hypothesis-specific abstract embedding model
- Reach out to tools developers willing to connect to our TS
- Improve ontologies for ecology (specifically invasion biology)
- Make ontologies more multilingual
- Combine ORKG templates with AI assistant and better connect with ontology / Biodiv Portal

AI for impact assessment / improving practice

- Using AI to describe impact
- Apply HoH and backwards inference approaches to synthesize knowledge on herbivore / deer impacts (which are extremely context dependent) to inform rewilding initiatives by policy / practitioners
- AI-boosted impact assessments of invasive species
- Use AI and other methods to help fill knowledge and data gaps in invasion science

- Using AI technology to promote free access to knowledge and promote power balance between publishers and researchers in science
 - Be part of our committee (internucleos AI (?))
 - How we can adapt what we have to ecology?

Tailoring causal graphs to ecology

- Target observation based causality prediction
 - How can information gained from the observation of a target (e.g. a chicken crossing or not crossing a road) be used to improve causality predictions
- Read more on time series causal inference and think about how we can use for insect populations
- What is needed to adapt Researchmaps to invasion ecology?
- Apply causal inference methods to ecological data
- Validate current work through causal inference approaches

- Try to use causal inference / causal graphs at ecological study design stage

Context dependence (has not been discussed further in a break-out group)

- Synthesis tools focusing on context dependence
- Continue thinking about how to model context dependence
- Alternative approaches to meta-analysis and external validity appraisal (to help 'Josh')

Questions outside of any of these clusters

- Broader use of mathematical models
- How does Josh perceive 'relevance' of research?
- Bigger picture: formalize and refine personas for practitioner (Josh) & journalist (Vanessa)
- Explore the roles of humans and types of machines for knowledge production
- Would like to take part in extension of Hi Knowledge graphs in ecology, specifically meta-system ecology, engage scientific community from that field, linking about possibility to use networks like GLEON for ontology development, training, annotation
- Make curation workflows more collaborative
- Formalize more hypotheses
- Build a data model for hypotheses
- Cleaning: Explore which ideas are actually new and interesting to AI and ecology literature
- Are there any challenges that are intrinsic to ecology?

Break-out group discussions

1 Causal networks and modeling hypotheses

Topic: How can we formalize hypotheses using causal networks, and how can this help us integrate data, evidence, and reasoning ?

1. Background

Tina and collaborators have started building causal networks to describe and connect major hypotheses in invasion biology. This formalization takes the shape of nodes (ecological entities or phenomena) connected by causal links (assumed causal relations between the two entities).

For example, some hypotheses can be simply formalized as:

Propagule pressure hypothesis:

Propagule pressure --increases--> Invasion success

Biotic resistance hypothesis:

Diversity of resident community --decreases--> Invasion success

These simple causal assumptions can also be "unpacked" to formalize the underlying causal steps we are assuming, for instance something like:

Propagule pressure --increases--> establishment success --increases--> invasion success

2. Formalizing hypothesis causal networks to enable logical reasoning/argumentation machines

We first started by discussing how we could add argumentation machines to causal networks of invasion hypotheses = reasoning on causal networks. An idea would be that :

1. First, we could build a causal model of major mechanisms in invasion biology, likely including basic community and population ecology mechanisms, and illustrating the causal mechanisms assumed in major hypotheses in invasion biology.
2. Second, we can formulate formal causal statements (see Argumentation machines presentation by Lars Bengel) based on the causal model that capture single hypotheses.
3. Third, we could use some form of argumentation machine to test those causal statements and evaluate whether they are "stable" (and other aspect of causal reasoning as presented by Lars).
4. Fourth, we could also use data to test the validity of these conclusions. (?)

(NOTE: Maud is writing this, and is not 100% sure that these steps are all possible or realistic - it is just a general idea)

We mainly asked Lars Bengel what characteristics of causal models were necessary for them to support logical argumentation.

- The causal models for an argumentation machine (as presented by Lars) are currently based on boolean relationships. This means that relationships can be: "causes" or "does not cause". Similarly, the variables (i.e. boxes or nodes in a causal graph) correspond to effects that can either exist or not (e.g. fever or no fever). This is not quite appropriate for most of the causality in our ecology networks, which are mostly about quantitative relationships, not absolute on/off effects (though these also exist, like for instance at least one initial introduction event is necessary for invasion to happen at all).
- Probabilistic approaches (not 0/1 but rather causal probability) are also possible, though more complicated.
- Causal models can also include "negative" causal links, which are read as X "inhibits" Y (visual code: —|)
- When a model is imperfect, and not all causes are modeled, (ie a given cause is not necessary and sufficient), then we can include "unknown causal variables" to allow argumentation machines to be more realistic (ie less absolute).
- We can also use AND / OR operators to account for these unknown variables. Example for propagule pressure:

Propagule pressure AND unknown var => establishment success

Establishment success AND unknown var => invasion success

Remaining problem:

Unclear how we can make the relationships quantitative as in "increase" or "decrease" in the formal causal model, unless we add probabilistic relationships perhaps?

- increases = causes + probability
- decreases = inhibits + probability

These are still imperfect as they describe the probability of a phenomenon happening, but not really a quantitative relationship telling us that when one variable increases then the other is likely to increase in response.

3. Automatic formalization of hypotheses based on natural language processing

Another aspect of hypotheses formalization is the idea of automatically generating causal graphs from natural language text, i.e. detecting hypotheses in a text and automatically representing them formally using concepts from ontologies and logic. Current work aims to use the INBIO ontology and the Hypotheses ontology (to be developed) to provide the concepts for such automatic formalization.

Alsayed noted that if the nodes of the causal network are simple variables like 'propagule pressure' without a qualifier like "high" or "low", then it is easier to have causal models which can be tested with data using causal inference methods (including Bayesian). However, such simplified interpretation of hypotheses are hard to obtain from natural language, in which modifiers are commonly used.

2 Using ontologies for AI

- How can ontologies be used for enhancing NLP tools?
- Discussion based on work Marc Brinner did in INAS
- Marc's idea at first was to use the definitions provided in the ontologies to enhance his classifier
- Other work suggests embedding ontologies in a way that there is more info taken from the ontology, e.g. hierarchical relationships between concepts
- Naouel suggested building on that (pretrained knowledge graph embeddings)
- But Marc was not convinced that it will be helpful, because this would mean losing all the pre-training he did
- He thought about rather starting from scratch with his classifier
- [Remained unresolved due to a lack of time]

3 Using AI for ontologies

How could AI be used for creating and enhancing ontologies?

- Idea could be to use AI (LLMs) for suggesting a first version of an ontology for a specific field or topic
- This version could then be checked and developed by experts
- A concrete idea could be to try this out for meta-system theory in ecology

4 AI-based synthesis tools for improving practice

What sorts of tools are needed to overcome the barriers to using research?

- Assumption that researchers will find our research useful.
- How do practitioners weigh different features when deciding to implement intervention that a study/studies have been on.
 - a question that has been asked in political science (Vivault et al. unpublished)
- Self-reflection on research comparing it with actually used practices.
- Coming back to context dependence, what type of context is actually relevant?
 - which factors are relevant to figure out or identify context dependency
 - which context do they consider to be most important?
 - maybe something similar for researchers or other groups - all say context is important
 - maybe diff practitioners care about different contexts?
 - could actually learn or compare that...
 - maybe need to split in ecosystems
 - management interventions itself target different aspects, maximize certain nature contributions to people.
- weigh studies by internal validity, way that practitioners do it is external validity
- many assumptions in us preparing these statements based on decisions we think are true or right - for ex. is there a management intervention needed? who decides
- especially with management decisions, always must be a dialogue
- idea is to turn tool into what might be a one-way solution into dialogic
- Pretty serious communication barriers
- power dynamic
- Can address some of those issues using data synthesis tools
- To facilitate transfer of data and knowledge between different communities, have to have the ability to make transfer effective.
- motivations to have projects designed from the beginning with practitioners or other stakeholders
- Challenge for researchers to find other stakeholders - finding a good number to do co-creation is often hard.
- Hope that this would be good motivation for practitioners to be in there from the start.
- Some standardized way to co-create knowledge or get feedback with community.
- Could focus on context-dependent factors - most relevant factors from your perspective.
- making decisions
- Have to describe conservation problem in a good way and
- Brainstorm conservation problem
- e.g. a new invasive species has appeared in your area

5 Towards an improved data landscape

Idea: Paper about how to improve the data landscape in ecology and invasion biology by compiling heterogeneous data sources into a common corpus.

In summary:

- data of different quality and quantity is leveraged from a variety of sources, spanning scientific publications, grey literature, curated datasets, practitioner reports, citizen science contributions, newspaper articles, archives, and loose sightings scraped from the web
- preliminary efforts in analysing the corpus to identify gaps for which little data is available (e.g. for species, locations, traits, environmental properties)
- Publish alongside the corpus all workflows that lead to its construction such as cleaning scripts and other code
- provide a usability guide

In more detail:

- harvesting knowledge from on the ground practice to feed it back into academia
- visualize the available data
- create an index similar to what we already have
- Question: how do practitioners weigh internal validity features vs external?
- how to interact with systematic search engines
- we need help discovering new information
 - e.g Africa as a challenge
- practitioners have reports that write what they found etc from the government
- grey lit
 - 1. finding creative ways to capture those data
 - 2. helping people to report those data --> citizen science
- Challenge of data quality: sometimes quantity > quality
- scraping random text from the web (news papers) may already be helpful
- how can we scrape informal data
- horizontal capturing techniques

Computer Science Need: Exact description of data and knowledge and where to get it

Data sources for corpus

- Academic Data
- Practitioner data
- Reports from societies, working groups
- Federal, state, local reports
- Newspapers
- Grey literature
- Citizen science on smartphones
- iNaturalist -> GBIF data (geocoded)
- Horizontal data gathering – scraping data from social (how to verify quality is a sticky issue)

- space for a discussion about how identifying data gaps is dependent on having clear research questions.
 - We will never have all data in the world.
 - In this sense we will always have gaps in our data corpus.
 - However what we are able to say is that the data that we have currently can or cannot be used to answer questions. This passes through matching data with theory.
- Difference between data gaps and knowledge gaps

6 Causal networks for ecologists

Topics that have been discussed in the group:

- Insight from ecology to neuroscience (researchmaps): it can be quite relevant to know about the target (i.e. the response variable) and the context because this could help informing the causal graph
 - Target observation based causality prediction
- Causal discovery with Researchmaps can help getting faster (i.e. with fewer experiments) to the 'true' causal graph
- Idea for a review / overview / survey paper:
 - What can causal graphs be used for?
 - What can't they be used for?
 - What is the difference to structural equation modeling?
 - Different causal inference approaches for ecology
 - Try some with examples
 - Of special interest: time series
 - This could demonstrate the potential of these approaches for ecology
 - E.g. for nature communications
- Researchmaps for ecology
 - Justin is interested in making the tool work for ecologists as well
 - We could try populating researchmaps.org with known causal networks
 - Alejandra tried it out briefly already with her data
 - It would be interesting to bring in ecology ontologies
 - Discuss in meetings with the researchmaps team
- Further ideas concerning the topic of causal modeling
 - Causes:
 - There is terminological confusion
 - Language issues
 - Granularity issues
 - Make sure to take that into account
 - How to partition between different causes and kinds of causes?
 - How to match the right kind of questions to the right tools?
 - We need a taxonomy of approaches
 - DAGs are an interesting path forward, because it is easily possible to turn them into knowledge graphs
 - A hypothesis could then be a view on this graph
 - Regard causal connections as probability distributions?